
STUDY OF THE UNIVERSE AS A SET OF SPATIAL CONTRACTIONS AND A RELATIVELY COMMON PHYSICAL OBJECT, VACUUM QUANTUM FLUCTUATIONS AS SPACE PROPERTIES, MODELIZATION OF A SCALAR FIELD OF "TEMPERATURE" INTRINSIC TO SPACE, HELICITY OF INITIAL SINGULARITY AND CONSEQUENCES ON THE MATTER OF THE PRIMORDIAL UNIVERSE, AND OPENINGS ON THE HYPOTHESIS OF THE MULTIVERSE

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August 20, 2024

ABSTRACT

We will study the Universe as a set of spatial contractions, as proposed at the beginning of the study of radial gravitational waves in 2019, in order to associate quantum fluctuations of the vacuum with variations in the curvature of Space-Time. We will then describe elementary particles as expressions of the properties of space itself, offering on this occasion a possible solution to the problem of dark matter, by quantum fluctuations of the vacuum causing pairs of weakly interactive particles emergence by variations in the curvature of Space-Time.

This conception of the Universe will then push us to attribute to space itself a scalar field of heat. We will then extract from these developments a cosmological constant Λ_T describing an expansion alternating between phases of acceleration and slowdown and predicting a progressive decline of dark energy that should already be perceptible.

By considering the Universe as a set of spatial contractions and therefore as a physical object that would be the expression of the properties of space itself, we will then be able to attribute to its initial singularity properties such as a magnetic moment of spin, preserved in the primordial Universe and causing, in fact, an asymmetry explaining the difference in probability in the set of particle-antiparticle pairs during the inflationary era. We would live today within the residue resulting from the bursting of a completely common singularity.

These reflections will strongly suggest the existence of the multiverse, modeled as a set of "bubbles" each containing an infinity of "bubbles" of universes emerging from the evaporation of the black holes populating it, then transmitting to these emerging universes their helicity and other characteristics. The properties of Space-Time and the entropy intrinsic to space itself would then be common to the universes of the multiverse, consequently preserving the fundamental laws of physics.

Keywords Gravitational wave · General Relativity · Quantization of Space-Time · Fine-structure constant · Feynman diagrams equations · Space temperature scalar field · Dark matter · Dark energy · Black holes · Multiverse

THE UNIVERSE IS NOT AN EXCEPTIONAL PHYSICAL OBJECT, HAS A HOT SPACE, WILL PROBABLY HAVE A LONGER HEAT DEATH, AND MAY HAVE BEEN ENDOWED WITH A QUANTUM SPIN - 2024

TRIBUTE

In memory of my friend, Sasha, a peace, environmental, and LGBT activist arrested and tortured by the Russian regime.

I started writing this paper last year when I came to pick you up and tried to save you from Russian authorities and prison.

I failed.

I will miss you until the last star in this universe stops shining. This is the reason that pushes me to dedicate this work to you and your fight for peace. I know this message will probably never reach you, but I couldn't stop thinking about you while writing. It will be a way of making our history indelible, in the midst of the brutality of this world.

Love and rage!

I will not publish in any journal that proposes to remove this message.

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1 Introduction

Based on the study of radial gravitational waves, the description of electromagnetic waves as a property of space, and the physical interpretation of the fine structure constant of 2019 [1], we will open here a reflection consisting of describing matter as a property of space. Indeed, based on the effects of gravitational waves on electromagnetic fields, on their polarization identical to that of electromagnetic waves, we have, among other things, postulated and then confirmed in a computational way that a radial gravitational wave had the same properties and could have the same nature as an electromagnetic wave. We will continue here the developments of 2019 by attempting an extension of this model to mass particles, considering the Universe as a set of spatial contractions resulting from a primordial singularity [2] of which it would have kept certain characteristics (its rotation [3, 4] and its quantum spin, among others). The Universe would then not be an exceptional physical object, no more than a black hole or a particle, since it is only the expression of the properties of Space-Time.

All this will allow us to formulate a hypothesis concerning the victory of matter over antimatter, to predict a destiny of the Universe different from that of the $\Lambda - CDM$ model, as well as the association of a scalar field of heat of space itself introducing entropy as an intrinsic property of our Space-Time.

2 The Universe as a physical object

Is the Universe a physical object capable of being studied in the same way as all those that compose it? In other words, could it not be endowed with characteristics comparable to its components and inherited from the initial singularity from which it would have come? It does indeed have a quadrupole rotation [3, 4], probably inherited from the primordial Universe as the no-hair theorem [5 - 9] would suggest.

We can then associate a Kerr metric [10] with its initial singularity and consider it as an ordinary physical object. It does indeed share interesting properties with the Kerr black hole from which it could have come, such as entropy [11, 12] among others. We can therefore try, as introduced, to see it as a physical object that is more of an expression of the properties of space, rather than as a particularly exceptional object. After all, why not?

3 The Universe as a set of spatial contractions

The study of radial gravitational waves in 2019 allowed us to describe electromagnetic waves and the photon associated with them as properties of space in the same way as gravitational waves [1]. This proposed to deepen this concept by proposing an opening of this relativistic conception of light to massive particles.

We will try here to overcome the difficulty of applying this model by focusing on a simple system: That of the encounter of two gravitational waves emitted by two identical sources ν and ζ , thus at an identical frequency ν_Ω and amplitude $A_{(r=l; \varphi=\frac{\pi}{2})_\Omega}$, at two points A and B (each distant by l from each source) in space, oriented in the reference frame of the source ν at angles $\varphi_{\nu A} = \frac{\pi}{2} - \varpi$ and $\varphi_{\nu B} = \frac{\pi}{2} + \varpi$, for $\varpi \rightarrow 0$ (in order to simplify the calculations that follow).

We will graphically represent the system as follows:

As seen in the 2019 study on radial gravitational waves, light can be thought of as a gravitational wave emitted in one direction [1], such that:

$$2\pi l A_{(r=l;\varphi=\frac{\pi}{2})\Omega} = A_{(r=l;\varphi=\frac{\pi}{2})\omega} \quad (1)$$

Either:

$$H_\omega = 2\pi l H'_\Omega = 2\pi l \frac{2G}{c^4} 2 \left(\frac{1}{2} m \left(f \frac{1}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right) \frac{(t-l/c)}{l} \quad (2)$$

Where H_ω and H'_Ω were respectively the expression of the amplitude of a radial gravitational wave and a gravitational wave propagating in all directions, from a non-binary source modeled from the equation corresponding to a binary system:

$$H_\Omega = \frac{2G}{c^4} \frac{\bar{Q}(t-l/c)}{l} \quad (3)$$

The polarizations, electromagnetic properties, and relativistic characteristics of ω and Ω were then identical. We can then consider that our source waves ν and ζ , of frequencies ν_Ω and identical amplitudes $A_{(r=l;\varphi=\frac{\pi}{2})\Omega}$, respond at each point A or B, to the relation linking the energy transported by the wave to its frequency and its amplitude (i.e. $E \propto A\nu$):

$$E = a\eta\nu \quad (4)$$

And this will be necessary, because at A and B, the spatial contraction of amplitude $2A_{(r=l;\varphi=\frac{\pi}{2})\Omega}$ at each point is no longer, momentarily, moving in a direction at the speed of light, which is impossible for such a wave, without a reaction having taken place to allow it. To try to solve this problem, we will study what happens locally, considering the value of the amplitude $A_{(r=l;\varphi=\frac{\pi}{2})\Omega}$ of the waves at A or B, so that $a\eta = \frac{h}{4}$ (the minimal quantization of the amplitude of an electromagnetic wave will facilitate the calculations for interpreting the reaction, since changing α would change the value of the charge q associated with the electric field S of the wave [1]), so that we can, as in the 2019 study, consider that all the energy transported at A and B by the waves is:

$$E_\Theta = \frac{X}{2\alpha} \nu \quad (5)$$

Where X is the structural constant related to the electric permittivity of vacuum such that:

$$X = \frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 c} \quad (6)$$

And where α is the fine structure constant:

$$\alpha = \frac{e^2}{2h\varepsilon_0 c} \quad (7)$$

Now, as seen in the 2019 study by the physical interpretation of the coupling constant as the ratio between the charge effect Z associated with the field S of the wave on a charge e (acting on a single wavelength λ) relative to the energy level carried by the wave [1], such that:

$$S = \frac{q}{\varepsilon_0 4\pi d^2} \quad (8)$$

And that:

$$Z = \frac{q}{\varepsilon_0} \quad (9)$$

For $q = e$ here, as seen in the 2019 study [1].

Having chosen $a\eta = \frac{h}{4}$ now allows us to understand what happened, by looking at the cross section σ of our quantity of energy, associated with the field S , during this reaction:

$$S = \frac{e}{\varepsilon_0 4\pi d^2} \quad (10)$$

Expressible:

$$S = \frac{\alpha \hbar c}{ed^2} \quad (11)$$

Then proportional to the coupling constant α , in the natural units system:

$$S \propto \alpha \quad (12)$$

Allowing us to use the differential of the cross section σ , corresponding to the square of the modulus of the scattering amplitude $f(\delta)$, allowing us to see the result of the reaction of the quantity of energy E_Θ scattered:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Pi} = |f(\delta)|^2 \quad (13)$$

With Π for the solid angle and δ for the diffusion angle.

Now, as seen earlier, the quantity of diffused energy is associated with an electric field $S \propto \alpha$, we can therefore deduce that $(\delta) \propto \sqrt{\alpha}$ and therefore that, in a natural units system with $\alpha = e^2$:

$$|f(\delta)|^2 \propto |\sqrt{\alpha}|^2 \quad (14)$$

And:

$$f(\delta) \propto -ie \quad (15)$$

Allowing us to express the scattering amplitude:

$$-if(\delta) = -ie\gamma^\mu \quad (16)$$

That is, a vertex of Feynman rules as calculated in quantum electrodynamics [13]:

At points A and B, the spatial contractions of amplitude $A_{(r=l; \varphi=\frac{\pi}{2})_\Omega}$ coming from the sources v and ζ then made it possible to generate an electron-positron pair [14], which could then disintegrate as follows:

The encounter of two gravitational waves is of course not the only situation allowing the appearance of particle pairs. But it was, from a computational point of view, the simplest way for our model to describe particles as properties of space.

We can then, based on the magnetic spin moment of the particle-antiparticle pair resulting from the reaction, deduce the mass m of said particles [15].

$$\vec{\mu}_S = L \frac{q}{2m} \vec{S} \quad (17)$$

With μ_S the spin magnetic moment, L the Landé factor, \vec{S} the spin, giving for the electron:

$$\mu_B = \frac{e\hbar}{2m_e} \quad (18)$$

Mass m_e of the electron conferred by its interaction with the BEEGHK field [15 - 18].

But this would not, of course, be the only pair that would have a probability of interaction or even of appearance. If any curvature G_{ij} implies the presence of energy distributed in Space-Time such that $G_{ij} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{ij}$, then the diversity of amplitude of spatial contractions and therefore of pairs of particles emerging from the "vacuum" should go beyond ordinary matter.

4 Other quantum fluctuations of the "vacuum" and "temperature" of space

4.1 Weakly interactive particles and dark matter

In the same way that it is not the only process that allows the emergence of particle-antiparticle duos, nothing prevents them from being the only pairs that can emerge. Quantities of energy, like our electron-positron pair, could appear, without charge or possibility of interaction with light, therefore without disintegration by mutual emission of electromagnetic waves as seen above. Said particles would then not interact with light, the electric field associated with these spatial contractions not allowing the previous relations to be verified. There would therefore not really be a reaction strictly speaking, but a probability of appearance and therefore of permanent presence of weakly interactive matter, like interactive matter (bosons, hadrons, fermions, whose variety and probability of appearance would be lower, since they represent a finer spectrum of possibilities). Being there, in fact, only because of the existence of spatial contractions associated with quantities of energy no longer moving momentarily at c , these "virtual" particles would have, in themselves, a short existence, but a probability of appearance inducing a permanent presence.

Indeed, for any generation of pairs, we would have a probability of presence $p(P)$ linked to the variations of the curvature of Space-Time G_{ij} and therefore to the probability of interaction of the quantities of energy transported, allowing us then to deduce that the equivalence:

$$EP_{ij} = T_{ij} \quad (19)$$

So that the variation in particle density is proportional to the variation in energy density:

$$\Delta(P_{00}) \propto \Delta(T_{00}) \quad (20)$$

Furthermore, if mass particles, interactive or weakly interactive, are only properties of space whose appearance is associated with probabilities of presence and interaction, the vacuum quantum fluctuations induced by variations in the curvature of Space-Time should be more intense near matter, that is, in the densest spaces, giving us a sort of "web" organized around the densest spaces of the Universe. The probability of presence $p(P)$ would then vary more strongly in the most contracted spaces and therefore where the energy density in space is greater.

The probability of presence of mass energy would then be distributed like a network connecting denser nodes, depending on the mass of the matter clusters constituting said nodes and their distances from each other.

In this graphical representation of $p(P)$, we can see that it is higher within matter clusters, where the mass energy density is higher, but also that it is higher in the shortest internodal spaces. Let us specify that here we have chosen a simple case, that of four identical and coplanar clusters, varying only the distance between them.

In a later Universe, we can assume that the distance between the massive sets will increasingly give a "web" shape to this network, with increasingly fine "threads" connecting increasingly distant nodes [19].

This then makes vacuum fluctuations eligible as an explanation for the significant and permanent presence of dark matter [20, 21], but not only. Indeed, considering that matter is a property of space in the same way as energy, where the probability of presence depends on the density of energy and matter, leads us to have to associate a "temperature" with space itself, which would then have a heat, that is, a level of its own energy depending on the density of the Universe and whose gradient is already perceived in the distribution of $p(P)$ in space. Thus, in a manner analogous to black holes [22 - 26], the more the Universe is dense in energy, the hotter its space is and generates massive pairs.

4.2 Scalar field of space "temperature"

If we consider a scalar field $K(r, u, w)$ for K the local heat such that:

$$K \propto \Phi \quad (21)$$

Where Φ is the local curvature, we obtain (in spherical coordinates) a scalar field, for a homogeneous temperature for any angle u and w :

$$K(r, u, w) = \frac{\Phi^{\frac{4}{3}} \pi r^3}{8\pi G c^{-4}} \quad (22)$$

That's to say:

$$K(r, u, w) = \frac{\Phi r^3 c^4}{6G} \quad (23)$$

Of gradient (in Cartesian coordinates):

$$\vec{\nabla} K(x, y, z) = \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x}(x, y, z), \frac{\partial K}{\partial y}(x, y, z), \frac{\partial K}{\partial z}(x, y, z) \right) \quad (24)$$

So:

$$\nabla K = \frac{\partial K}{\partial x} \mathbf{k}_1 + \frac{\partial K}{\partial y} \mathbf{k}_2 + \frac{\partial K}{\partial z} \mathbf{k}_3 \quad (25)$$

And (in spherical coordinates):

$$\nabla K(r, u, w) = \frac{\partial K}{\partial x} \kappa_r + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial K}{\partial y} \kappa_u + \frac{1}{\sin(u)r} \frac{\partial K}{\partial z} \kappa_w \quad (26)$$

So, in tensor form:

$$\nabla K = \frac{\partial K}{\partial v^i} g^{ij} \kappa_j \quad (27)$$

Implying that the average heat density of space Ξ_K depends on the global curvature of the Universe Υ , itself expressible as a function of the average mass energy density:

$$\Upsilon(\Xi_{E_m}) = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \Xi_{E_m} \quad (28)$$

Allowing us to deduce that $\Xi_K \propto \Upsilon(\Xi_{E_m})$ as induced in the previous subsection.

Now, as seen above, the heat density of space is the sum of the energy density of the field associated with the curvature of Space-Time Ξ_{E_g} (where $\Xi_{E_g} \propto \Upsilon(\Xi_{E_m})$) and the radiation energy density Ξ_{E_γ} (non-zero) [1, 27], such that:

$$\Xi_K = \Xi_{E_g} + \Xi_{E_\gamma} \quad (29)$$

We can deduce that, since Ξ_{E_m} and Ξ_{E_γ} satisfy the second law of thermodynamics, then Ξ_K also undergoes the effects of entropy. We will thus have, for $\Delta \Xi_K = \Xi_{K t_2} - \Xi_{K t_1}$:

$$\frac{\Delta \Xi_K}{\Xi_K} < 0 \quad (30)$$

Allowing us to conclude, due to the decrease in heat density and respecting the law of conservation of energy, that a hot space naturally expands, providing answers to the questions asked in 2019 [1, 28].

Allowing us to determine that if:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\Delta \Xi_K}{\Xi_K} < 0 \\ \frac{\Delta \Xi_{E_m}}{\Xi_K} < 0 \end{array} \right.$$

(31)

Then we would observe a space dilation [29] due to its heat opposing the gravitational attraction due to its mass energy density, so that the expansion factor Ψ would be articulated as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Psi \propto \Xi_K \\ \Psi \propto \Xi_{E_m}^{-1} \end{array} \right.$$

(32)

Such as:

$$\Psi = \frac{8\pi G c^{-4} \Xi_K}{\Upsilon(\Xi_{E_m})} > 1 \quad (33)$$

All of which allows us to extract a cosmological constant Λ_Γ :

$$\Lambda_\Gamma = 8\pi G c^{-4} \Xi_K - \Upsilon(\Xi_{E_m}) \quad (34)$$

We can then predict an expansion of the Universe alternating between phases of high average heat density of space and high average mass energy density:

At time A , where the Universe passes from its initial singularity to a primordial Universe in full inflationary era I , Ξ_K and Ψ are strong, causing then an increase of Ξ_{E_m} , already triggering the process of decrease of the factor Ψ at the next intermediate time B , remaining however greater than 1, as seen above.

At time B , where the Universe enters its first era of decelerated expansion II , Ξ_{E_m} is strong, while Ψ is weakened, implying a progressive increase of the importance of Ξ_K in the factor Ψ , triggering then its programmed growth at the next intermediate time.

At time C , where the Universe passes from era II to a Universe in an era of accelerated expansion III (admittedly less important than era I), Ξ_K and Ψ are strong, causing then an increase of Ξ_{E_m} , already triggering the process of decrease of the factor Ψ at the next intermediate time, around which we should be located today.

At time D , according to the Λ_Γ model, we should observe an era IV with characteristics similar to era II , at a lower degree of importance and in a Universe that, from era to era, is less and less dense, alternating between periods of accelerated expansion and decelerated expansion that are shorter and shorter, Ψ thus oscillating less and less amply, taking into account the high rigidity of Space-Time that translates the constant factor $2Gc^{-4}$ seen above.

If, in Einstein's equation [30]:

$$G_{ij} = R_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}g_{ij} + \Lambda g_{ij} = \chi T_{ij} \quad (35)$$

We have $\Lambda = \Lambda_\Gamma$, so we can predict that Ξ_K and Ξ_{E_m} will tend to 0, but with a smaller average Ψ factor than in the $\Lambda - CDM$ model [31, 32], announcing the evaporation of the last black holes [22 - 26, 33] and a thermal death of the Universe [34] more distant. But, and this is an important point, we should already observe an entry into the IV era and therefore a progressive decline of dark energy. We will therefore know by observational means whether Λ_Γ is the unique component of Λ or whether the cosmological constant is parameterizable by $\Lambda * + \Lambda_\Gamma$, where Λ^* is a constant or a set of additional constants resulting from unknown phenomena and processes. In this paper, we will

produce predictions based on the Λ_Γ model and consider entropy as an intrinsic property of space itself, in line with the 2019 study [1] and the developments of the present study.

5 Quantum spin of the primordial Universe and consequences

5.1 Magnetic moment of spin and helicity

If we can associate three parameters to a black hole: mass, kinetic moment, and charge defining its area A [22, 23, 35], such that:

$$A = 4\pi(2m^2 - q^2 + 2m\sqrt{m^2 - q^2 - \frac{J^2}{m^2}}) \quad (36)$$

For m the mass, q the charge, and J the angular momentum. A black hole quickly equilibrates to neutral charge (since it attracts particles of opposite charge like a magnet if it is charged), we assume that Kerr-Newman black holes [36] are quite rare. We can simplify, in most cases:

$$A = 4\pi(2m^2 + 2m\sqrt{m^2 - \frac{J^2}{m^2}}) \quad (37)$$

It is also known, since the theorization of Bekenstein-Hawking radiation inducing their evaporation [22 - 26], that its parameters are alterable by the analogous parameters of the particles that enter its event horizon [22 - 26, 35] (charge, magnetic moment, etc ...).

We will go further here, considering, as formulated above, that since these parameters, in particular the kinetic moment and therefore the magnetic moment which depends on it have the same nature, from a particle to a black hole, since being the expression of the properties of space itself for any spatial contraction.

Now, going back to the Big Bang and the initial singularity that gave rise to it [2], we can, even if it had been neutrally charged, in the same way as a neutrino [37] or a neutron [38], associate it with a spin kinetic moment and therefore a spin magnetic moment $\vec{\mu}_S(m, \vec{S})$. The resulting helicity would be important. In the event of evaporation of the initial singularity, it would be, as seen above, conserved, from the singularity to the resulting primordial Universe, otherwise the principle of conservation of energy would be violated. This would thus be an application of a sort of quantum no-hair theorem [5 - 9].

5.2 Victory of matter over antimatter

We would then have, among the particles and antiparticles produced, an asymmetry, the average helicity of the components of the primordial Universe having to be in the same direction as that of the singularity. We can then assume that the particles having a helicity in the same direction as said singularity would be more numerous, interacting more significantly with the part of matter with which it is supposed to interact, playing a role in the formation of a form of matter particles ρ rather than their opposites ϱ , inducing:

$$p(P_\rho) > p(P_\varrho) \quad (38)$$

A good candidate to be this tipping particle in the matter-antimatter struggle would be the neutrino [39]. Neutrally charged, but endowed with a kinetic and magnetic moment, of low mass therefore easier to see appearing in abundance. If it is today little interactive, due to its low cross section, and therefore difficult to detect due to the low density of the Universe, it could, in a universe where Ξ_{E_m} was more important, have had a significant importance in the formation of matter and more massive particles (baryons, mesons like the kaon, ...), where the antineutrinos, less numerous and with a weaker potential for emergence and interaction, would have quantitatively interacted less with antimatter. It is of course a credible candidate, although in the absence of more information beyond the Planck wall, it would be imprudent to affirm that it would be with certainty the tipping particle. We will therefore formulate that the seesaw particle, made possible by the attribution of a quantum spin to the Universe, could be the neutrino.

The current universe would then be the residue of a gigantic set of disintegrations [40], in which matter would have dominated antimatter by violation of symmetry due to the properties of the initial singularity, all generated by the bursting of the latter, ultimately as common as those of our black holes: Rotating, endowed with a quantum spin, ... It would therefore not be a particularly exceptional physical object.

6 Implications and conclusions

6.1 Implications relating to the Universe and the black holes that populate it

6.1.1 Contributions

For the Λ_T model, the Universe, resulting from the dissipation singularity - that is, an infinite spatial contraction [2, 3, 10], rotating [3 - 10], would have seen the emergence of matter during its inflationary period [41]. An external observer could associate a mass energy with said singularity. But, from the point of view of an observer located within the resulting Universe, it would be something else. Indeed, any observer would be a set of finite spatial contractions, portions of an initial infinite contraction. In other words, if, from the point of view of an external observer, the Universe would be located in a finite and short space and time, from the point of view of an observer located inside, it would not be. This would explain the estimates of the globally flat curvature of the Universe from observations by the WMAP satellite [42 - 45].

Similarly, each black hole, once evaporated and its singularity dissipated, could give rise to a new universe within ours. From our point of view, it would be a "flash" on the cosmological time scale [25], but from the point of view of an observer located inside this "flash", it would be in another universe, whose properties (spin in particular) would have been inherited from the evaporated black hole.

6.1.2 Concordances

Concerning the evaporation of black holes, there is also a concordance between the Λ_T model and what is predicted by the current Bekenstein-Hawking radiation model [22 - 26]. Indeed, if we imagine a generation of two neutrino-antineutrino pairs on the event horizon of a black hole (considering that it will absorb as many neutrinos as antineutrinos), by the vacuum fluctuation process described in sections 3 and 4, we certainly have:

$$E_{m_{BH}} > E_{m_{FV}} \quad (39)$$

But above all an energy E_g provided by the black hole greater than the energy from the exterior of the black hole E'_g (negligible) for all generations of pairs, so that:

$$E_g - E'_g \rightarrow E_g \quad (40)$$

We would then have:

Here, to illustrate this process simply, the antineutrino outside the event horizon statistically ends up decaying with a neutrino, the Universe being made up of more matter than antimatter (see 5.2), while the neutrino emitted outside the horizon has less chance of decaying. We therefore have, at the end of these fluctuations, γ' and a neutrino ν outside the horizon and γ beyond the horizon.

The black hole providing most of the energy to the reactions, we finally obtain:

$$E'_\gamma - E_\gamma \rightarrow 4m_\nu c^2 \quad (41)$$

For $|E'_\gamma| = |E_\gamma|$. So :

$$\begin{cases} E'_{\gamma} \rightarrow 2m_{\nu}c^2 \\ E_{\gamma} \rightarrow -2m_{\nu}c^2 \end{cases}$$

(42)

Where E'_{γ} is the energy moving away from the black hole and E_{γ} is the energy falling into the black hole, absorbing "negative" energy, as if the vacuum were taking gravitational energy from it with each vacuum quantum fluctuation. The mass energy $E_{m_{BH}}$ of the black hole decreases in the same way as predicted by the Bekenstein-Hawking radiation model [22 - 26] and in agreement with the Standard Model.

6.2 The multiverse as a set of "bubbles" of universes

We could then consider that our Universe would itself be contained in an infinitely large multiverse containing an infinite number of universes in the making [2].

The conditions of emergence and the functioning of said universes, themselves expressions of the properties of the space common to all universes, there would therefore be no significant change from one universe to another according to the Λ_{Γ} model, in terms of physical laws.

Each universe would then be a "bubble" containing an infinity of "bubbles" of universes responding to the same laws and whose composition as well as internal structure would depend on the characteristics of the black hole at the origin of each bubble.

6.3 Entropy as a property of Space-Time

Consequently, entropy - a property of space itself in the same way as gravitation, would be a common feature of all the "bubbles" of the multiverse, according to the Λ_{Γ} model.

Destined to a slower thermal death than in the $\Lambda - CDM$ model, the "bubbles" would have a Ξ_{E_m} and a Ξ_K tending towards 0, without ever reaching it, due to the emergence of an infinity of other "bubbles". These would also move away from each other at speeds greater than that of light, due to a continuous and perpetual expansion of space having taken over gravity.

7 Experiments and possible openings

7.1 Experiments

Three possibilities of experimentation could be (theoretically) within our reach and give favorable signs to the Λ_{Γ} models:

- The observation of an increase in the $p(P)$ of mass energy and vacuum state fluctuations during variations in the curvature of Space-Time (as during the capture of gravitational waves large enough to obtain a significant result [46 - 48]).
- The observation of a progressive decline of dark energy, which should already be perceptible.
- The highlighting of a spin conservation mechanism as well as general properties during the laboratory simulation of a "bubble" of a universe on a quantum scale. We will monitor in particular the evolution of the QSIMFP [49], its predictions [50] and results, which could give us the beginnings of an answer regarding the possibility of being in a multiverse and, if applicable, the functioning of a primordial universe. This would in any case be a good start to shed light on the different multiverse models emitted.

7.2 Openings

The Λ_{Γ} model could be extended to quantum chromodynamics in order to cover the entire $SU(3)SU(2)U(1)$ gauge group of the standard model, i.e. the strong force and the electroweak force. It would be necessary to note in particular that the interactions studied would be able to be described as expressions of the properties of space itself.

8 (Almost) final word

Physics has always pushed back certainties. We first thought that the Earth was the only center of the Universe, then that our stellar system was special, as if everything revolved around the Sun. We then discovered that it was part of something even bigger: The Milky Way. All this to finally understand that it was only one galaxy among billions of others, in a perhaps infinite Universe. But what if the latter was not the ultimate step in our understanding? And what if it was ultimately not as exceptional as we would be led to think? In any case, this is what the conclusions of this paper suggest.

Acknowledgment

I thank Gabriel Fournier for having given his time, outside of his studies, to the compilation of references, the structuring of this article in due form, and, more generally, compensating for the obstacles due to the loss of the use of my right eye (reading, writing, ...).

Competing interests

The author declares no competing interests.

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